

THE PUBLICATIONS OF
PROFESSOR LINUS PAULING

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This compendium supplants the slightly incomplete list by category of scientific publications covering the period 1923–1967 compiled by G. Albrecht (“Scientific Publications of Linus Pauling,” in *Structural Chemistry and Molecular Biology: A Volume Dedicated to Linus Pauling* by his Students, Colleagues, and Friends, A. Rich and N. Davidson eds., W. H. Freeman, San Francisco, 1968, pp. 888–907) and the list of publications covering the period 1966–1988 compiled by Z. S. Herman and D. B. Munro (*Croatica Chemica Acta* **61**, C9–C34 (1988)).

Where a paper has been published in more than one place, all reprints of it are listed with the original publication. Two types of descriptors (e. g., “article ; three”) are employed and follow the symbol “ \Rightarrow ”. The first describes the sort of publication and the second the subject area. This is done according to the following classification scheme:

- one. The Structure of Crystals.
- two. Quantum Mechanics.
- three. The Nature of the Chemical Bond.
- four. The Determination of the Structure of Molecules by the Diffraction of Electrons.
- five. Electronic Theory and Structure of Metals and Intermetallic Compounds.
- six. The Structure and Properties of Hemoglobin and Other Proteins.
- seven. Structure of Antibodies and the Nature of Serological Reactions.
- eight. Chemistry in Relation to Biology and Medicine.
- nine. The Structure of Atomic Nuclei.
- ten. Other Fields of Science.
- eleven. Orthomolecular Medicine.
- twelve. Vitamins and Health.
- thirteen. Vitamin C and Cancer.
- fourteen. World Peace.
- fifteen. Education.
- sixteen. Forewords to Books.
- seventeen. Letters to the Editor; Book Reviews.
- eighteen. Newspaper and Magazine Articles.
- nineteen. The History and Philosophy of Science.
- twenty. Books.

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